

This is a postprint of our contribution to the HDH2017 conference, which took place in Málaga from 18 to 20 October 2017. The short paper was published in the “Libro de resúmenes” (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2581090>), where it can be found on pp. 173–176. In order to make the paper more accessible and easier to cite, we decided to publish this postprint. The text remains the same, we only updated our affiliations and outdated URLs. – F. F., C. M., 10 January 2024.

Easy Linavis

(Simple Network Visualisation for Literary Texts)

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The analysis of social networks extracted from literary texts has grown into a subfield of Digital Literary Studies in recent years (Moretti, 2011; Jannidis, 2017). Our own research is based on the automatic extraction from larger corpora. Operationalising this kind of extraction is a non-trivial, often times ambiguous act, even if we talk about highly structured texts like plays (Fischer et al., 2015).

The resulting network graph might be contained in a file format as simple as CSV (comma separated values). A list of a character’s social interactions with other characters in a play would look something like this:

```
Source,Target,Weight
Electra,Evarista,10
Electra,Gil,1
Electra,La Sombra,1
Electra,Mariano,4
Electra,Marqués,13
Electra,Máximo,14
Electra,Pantoja,10
Electra,Patros,4
```

The relations listed above were extracted from Benito Pérez Galdós’s 5-act play “Electra”, which premiered in 1901. To achieve this result, one could simply browse a book or scroll through a digital copy of this book and count all shared speech acts (weight) of all characters – a laborious and error-prone act.

Instead, this information could be collected in an intermediary scene-by-scene format like this:

```

# ACTO PRIMERO
## ESCENA PRIMERA
José
Marqués
## ESCENA II
Don Urbano
Marqués
## ESCENA III
Cuesta
Marqués
Don Urbano
## ESCENA IV
Cuesta
Patros
## ESCENA V
Cuesta
Pantoja
...

```

This intermediary list of acting/speaking characters per scene is much more controllable, and translating this simple format into a working CSV file is a matter of just a handful of lines of code. We facilitated this process by creating an easy-to-use online tool for that, “Easy Linavis”. An example can be seen in Figure 1.

We used React (<https://react.dev/>) for building the interface of our tool. The CSV format is created live, based on the content entered (or copied and pasted) by the user in the left row.

Fig. 1: Pérez Galdós's play “Electra” in Easy Linavis.

Once the extraction of all scenes is finished, the resulting lines in the middle row can be saved in a 4-column CSV file, ready to be imported into Gephi or other network visualisation software. The graph in the right part of the screen is also generated live and is meant as a first impression of the resulting graph. We used sigma.js for this (<https://www.sigmajs.org/>) and chose a force-directed layout algorithm to generate the graph.

The code for our project was released as open source and can be obtained on GitHub (<https://github.com/dracor-org/ezlinavis>). The software can be run on your own server or cloned to your computer and run locally:

```
git clone https://github.com/dracor-org/ezlinavis.git
cd ezlinavis
npm install
npm test
npm start
```

We also set up a showcase instance at <https://ezlinavis.dracor.org/>, which contains a handful of example files.

The purpose of Easy Linavis is not to compete with more sophisticated methods of extracting networks from literary texts, but is intended for didactic use in teaching, to take first steps from theory to practice. We will also address the adaptability and extensibility of the tool.

References

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